

FORMING CREATIVE SKILLS AND PROFESSIONAL CULTURE IN FUTURE

FOREIGN LANGUAGE TEACHERS

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Annotation: In this article, the future foreign language teachers who teach English should have thoroughly mastered modern pedagogic achievements, techniques and technology, didactics and teaching methodology. Such teachers are successful. It is explained in detail that in order to achieve this success, the teacher should first of all rely on the rules of lesson organization developed in the didactic direction when preparing for classes.

Keywords: English language teachers, skills, communication, achievement, technique.

The political, socio-economic and cultural changes taking place in the life of our country undoubtedly have an impact on the activities of higher education institutions. Now, the task of higher education institutions is not only to give knowledge to the future specialist, but also to form his personality, to teach him practical professional skills and competence, culture, creativity, and creative independence. Because being a mature professional starts with initiative and creativity.

But today it can be observed that there are contradictions between the fundamental training and professional methodical and psychological training of future foreign language teachers. This problem can be solved by developing their creativity and creative independence.

The results of pedagogical practice and observation showed that many students studying in higher educational institutions have low creativity skills, or rather, the ability to effectively organize their creative activities. In our opinion, the main reason for this is the conflict between the existing system of education and its new goals and tasks, as well as between the traditional methodology of professional education and modern achievements of psychological sciences. Now, it is important for future foreign language teachers to have professional, psychological-pedagogical and fundamental training, to master specific methods and technologies, to be creative and creatively independent, to be able to design pedagogical activities, and to develop their own research position.

This issue puts on the agenda the problem of improving the professional training of future foreign language teachers on the basis of completely new principles, reforming the teaching system, developing the technology of designing various pedagogical objects and, in connection with it, revising the content of education in higher educational institutions.

The following areas of development of creativity and creative independence of future foreign language teachers can be noted:

- to explain to future foreign language teachers that creativity is a factor of increasing the quality of professional training, the important and significant aspects of creative independence;
- to understand that knowing the laws of objective reality, events and information about them is the basis of creative independence;
- creation of necessary conditions for the development of creative independence of students;
- to provide a positive emotional environment in the process of educational activities, to create internal motivation in students and to give them an opportunity to test their professional abilities.

When designing the content of educational programs aimed at developing the creativity of future pedagogues, attention should be paid to the following:

- to provide fundamental knowledge to future foreign language teachers, to introduce them to the methods and means of creative pedagogical activity, to achieve that they acquire and demonstrate not abstract theoretical knowledge, but specific skills and qualifications;
- creation of conditions for acquiring experience of professional creativity and independent activity;
- formation of the following creative qualities in a person: motivational activity, professional orientation, responsibility, hard work, respect for national culture and the desire to preserve and develop it, emotional-value attitude to the environment, etc.

Updating the content of higher pedagogical education implies the formation of two important skills in future pedagogues:

- the ability to perform creative activities (setting the goal of independent work, analyzing non-standard situations and drawing appropriate conclusions, mastering the methodology of solving educational and research problems, searching for alternative means and methods of solving problems, observing and systematizing experimental results, etc.);
- independent knowledge development skills (planning of independent work, use of modern references and educational materials related to source studies, including the use of computer databases, writing abstracts, studying and analyzing various information, planning public presentations, preparing lectures and summaries, control of work and evaluation of results and other works).

Effective ways to develop students' creativity are problem-based teaching and research. In doing so, they acquire new knowledge based on implementation of design work and solving non-standard pedagogical situations. Such methods are introduced through different forms of teaching: problem lectures, planning one or more pedagogical situations (which allows them to see the subject and social aspects of their future professional activity); problem-based

laboratory exercises, practical exercises, the tasks of which are gradually becoming more complicated; creative independent works performed outside of school hours.

In order to train future foreign language teachers in the way of scientific thinking, in order to form their creative research skills, it is desirable to prepare more assignments and analytical educational materials, to regularly carry out experiment-research works.

Of course, it is important to develop students' creative initiatives, creativity, and intellectual abilities. But it depends on many factors, first of all, on the human qualities and creativity of teachers and mentors. It is possible to achieve effective results by instilling in the hearts of students a love of science, an interest in learning, and a passion for creativity.

For this, every student needs to constantly work on himself, work on improving the level of knowledge, culture, upbringing, spirituality and enlightenment.

He studies educational processes in the formation of professional culture, directs them to the goal and controls them. Therefore, it is important to pay special attention to the teaching of vocational education subjects in the formation of professional culture in students.

In this, future foreign language teachers are formed with knowledge, skills and abilities about the subject, goals and tasks of pedagogy, theoretical foundations, the relationship of professional education pedagogy with other disciplines, professional education methodology and scientific research methods, didactics, educational theory.

In the field of psychology, theoretical and practical knowledge, skills and abilities are developed about the characteristics of pedagogical activity, the basics of psychology, types of economic and production activities and their structure, management psychology, professional psychology.

In the course of the science of the complex of didactic tools, knowledge, skills and abilities are formed about the theory of didactic education, the teaching process, the principles and laws of education, the content of education, the methods of teaching in vocational colleges, educational tools, and the forms of organizing the educational process.

In the physiology and hygiene of puberty, knowledge, skills and competences are formed about the hygiene and physiology of adolescence, adolescent endocrinology, puberty, nutritional hygiene, genetics and modern concepts of heredity.

Pedagogical skill - the essence of pedagogical skill in the science of pedagogy-psychology, pedagogical abilities and skills, pedagogical communication, the teacher's skill in the lesson and educational work, develops the skills and skills of organizing the pedagogical conditions of the teacher's skill.

Vocational education methodology - the subject, tasks and scientific foundations of the vocational education teaching methodology course, methods used in the study of vocational education, preparation and conducting of vocational education methodology classes, knowledge of the methods used in the vocational education lesson, the use of visual aids and technical tools , equips with skills and competencies.

Professional skills - philosophical and methodological foundations of professional skills, methods of research in professional skills, trends of the main development system in imparting professional knowledge, information about foreign professional skills.

Modern pedagogical technologies - the goals and objectives of the science of pedagogical technology, the study and application of modern pedagogical and information technologies, modern pedagogy and information technologies, methods of the educational process, providing students with complete information about pedagogical technology and the stages of the development of educational technologies, knowledge about the design of educational activities , skills and competencies are formed.

Therefore, the future foreign language teachers teaching English must have thoroughly mastered modern pedagogic achievements, techniques and technology, didactics and teaching methods. Such teachers are successful. In order to achieve this success, the teacher should first of all rely on the rules of lesson organization developed in the didactic direction when preparing for classes. For this:

- determining the purpose of the lesson, that is, defining what should be achieved;
- determining the size of the subject to be studied, that is, determining the subject according to the set goal and students' capabilities, connecting knowledge with practice;
- formation of didactic issues of the lesson, achieving the goal as a result of solving them sequentially;
- choosing the most optimal combination of methods and methods in accordance with the set goal;
- to clearly organize the lesson, to determine its structure, to follow the plan, to ensure the integrity of the lesson, unity of teacher and student activities, to manage the teacher's learning process;
- all didactic issues planned in the lesson should be solved in the lesson, not given to students as homework.

Thus, organizing classes in this way is one of the elements of the teacher's professional culture. However, professional culture and skills, success in pedagogy depends on the formation of creativity and professional culture in students, that is, future foreign language teachers.

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